

THE PHONETICS OF DISCOURSE MARKERS IN ENGLISH CONVERSATION

Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi

Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

named after Mirzo Ulugbek

The Faculty of Psychology, the department of Foreign languages

Philology and foreign languages

Scientific advisor: nafisateshaboyeva@gmail.com

Mamarajabova Diyora Akrom qizi

Student of group 402-22

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17971637>

Abstract: Discourse markers play an important role in the coherence of discourse and facilitate communication. It has been also argued that EFL students need not only the grammatical competence but also discourse knowledge to be able to effectively maintain a conversation. Therefore, the present study investigates the use and functions of discourse markers as used by EFL students at Faculty of Social Sciences in Kuwait. It also aims to investigate the differences between high and low proficient learners in using such discourse markers. The study adopts the Fung and Carter's (2007) model in which the discourse markers are classified into four categories, namely, interpersonal, structural, inferential and cognitive.

Key words: Discourse markers; English conversations; EFL students; speaking proficiency.

Language learners usually argue that they have an interest to develop their language ability in speaking and to speak a language like native speakers (Sadegh & Yarandi, 2014). Speaking an L2 fluently has become a must especially for the learners who wish to pursue their study in some particular fields of business and education. Moreover, fluency in L2 speaking is considered to be one of the aims that L2 teachers want to achieve with language students using different methods of teaching to make their students fluent in the L2 communication. Brown (2003) proposed that communicative language strategies could assist learners in communicating fluently with whatever proficiency they happen to have, in many situations among which the ability to use hesitations, pauses, speed, and discourse markers efficiently. In fact, the use of discourse marker represents one of the significant dimensions of natural spoken discourse and both L2 teachers and discourse analysts can hardly afford to disregard its importance in spoken language (Sadegh & Yarandi, 2014). In the last two decades, studying discourse markers has become significant in linguistics and much research has been conducted and consequently several approaches to this concept have been offered. One of the scholars who brought up the significance of discourse markers is Schiffrin (1987) who defined discourse markers as "sequentially dependent elements which bracket units of talk", units that include such entities as tone units, speech acts, sentences propositions, and the exact nature of which she intentionally leaves vague. Schiffrin named them 'discourse markers' and proposed that, conversely, they themselves might define "some yet undiscovered units of talk". Moreover, Schiffrin defined "discourse markers at a more theoretical level as members of a functional class of verbal and nonverbal devices which provide contextual coordinates for ongoing talk". She argued that discourse markers include a broad class of discourse markers lexicalized phrases (you know, I mean), adverbs (now, then), interjections (oh, uh, um, huh) and conjunctions (e.g. and, but, or). Furthermore, she proposed that discourse markers do not simply fit into a

linguistic class claiming that non-verbal gestures as well as paralinguistic features are possible discourse markers.

Moreover, Brown and Yule (1983) defined discourse markers as “metalingual comments in which the speaker specifically comments on how what he is saying is to be taken”. They contended that the thematized metalingual comments are not combined with the content representation that the recipients are building. They added that discourse markers just give them directions about the structure and kind of mental representation they should be developing.” Bright (1992) also maintained that discourse markers like uh, um, err and you know could be considered as a set of linguistic items which function in the textual, expressive, social and cognitive domains. Besides, Fraser (1999) viewed discourse markers as “a class of lexical expressions drawn primarily from a class of conjunctions, adverbs and prepositional phrases and with certain exceptions they signal a relationship between the interpretations of the segment they introduce S1 and the prior segment S2.” It is commonly acknowledged that discourse markers as multifunctional linguistic units which support interaction, serve to join an utterance with its context and/or co-text (RomeroTrillo, 2013). Discourse markers are also important elements of language in speech, or in any kind of interactive non-face-to-face spoken or face-to-face exchange. They are used in naturally occurring conversation such as phone conversation or classroom talk, not only to develop coherence, but also to serve other significant functions like regulating turns as well as signaling utterances with actions related to those in prior units (Nookam, 2010). They could also assist L2 learners not only to sound more natural, but also to deal with the challenges encountered while speaking a foreign language (Kovač & Jakupčević, 2020). Discourse markers establish the interactive bonds among interlocutors, provide guidance for the speakers and listeners in communication and help them reach conclusions about the direction the communication is heading in through signaling the communicative intention of speakers (Moreno, 2008). This makes discourse markers significant elements of spontaneous and unplanned communication (Tree, 2010). In this connection, Hartmann and Stork (1976) argued that an individual could be considered as fluent in speaking a language if s/he is able to precisely utilize its structures while focusing on content rather than form, employing the patterns and units automatically at normal conversational speed when they are required.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Nafisa, T. (2023). NOUNS AND THEIR GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 292-297.
2. Nafisa, T., & Marina, S. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN TESL AND TEFL CLASSROOMS. *International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research*, 465-469.
3. Nafisa, T. (2023). THE USA ECONOMY, INDUSTRY, MANUFACTURING AND NATURAL RESOURCES OF GREAT BRITAIN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RECENTLY SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHER'S THEORY*, 1(9), 94-97.
4. Nafisa, T. (2023). Secondary ways of word formation. In *Conference on Universal Science Research* (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 109-112).
5. Aijmer, K. (2004). Pragmatic markers in spoken interlanguage. *Nordic Journal of English Studies*, 3(1), 173-190.

6. Ali, E.A. & Mahadin, R.S. (2015). The Use of Interpersonal Discourse Markers by Students of English at the University of Jordan, *World English Journal (AWEJ)*, 6.4, Pp. 306 -319.
7. Arya, T. (2022). Exploring Discourse Marker Use in Thai University Students" Conversations; *Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 13, 1: pp. 247-267.
8. Bright, W. (ed.) (1992). *International encyclopedia of linguistics*. New York: Oxford University Press.
9. Brown, G., & Yule, G. (1983). *Discourse Analysis*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.